

Evaluation and characterization of modernization of the food industry

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Abstract

The article uses the expert survey method to assess the process of modernization of the food industry. Initially, the article provides a brief description of the scientific sources on the topic. The issues of selection of experts, determination of their qualifications, assessment of the degree of closeness and consistency of the expert opinion were then discussed. In the last part of the article, all the results obtained are summarized.

Introduction

Economic reforms aimed at accelerating economic development and improving the welfare of the population in our country are yielding positive results. In particular, the role of government programs in the efficient use of land, water and other natural resources and long-term work in meeting the needs of the population in food, which has become one of the global problems, is growing.

The development of the food industry will have a strong impact on the development of services such as banking, insurance, communications, trade and transport. In particular, many sectors of the service sector are directly dependent on the food industry, and without these services, food products will simply not be available. The food industry will also have a positive impact on the development of research, wholesale and retail trade, and catering.

Due to the above, the sustainable and balanced development of the food industry is of great importance today, and the modernization of its internal sectors plays an important role in achieving such goals.

«Economists estimate that additional economic growth of 2-3% per year can be

achieved through development based on domestic scientific and technological potential, and 7-8% per year through the introduction of the latest technologies in the modernization process.»

Modernization of the food industry is a process of technological innovation aimed at increasing the competitiveness of products, which is a means of overcoming technological backwardness in the industry and allows for more efficient use of labor and material resources. In turn, the results of the process of technical and technological innovations determine the conditions for the rapid development of high-tech competitive production.

The main goal of modernization of industrial sectors is to modernize the industry and its products, accelerate innovative development through the development of priority industries with high science capacity, increase the competitiveness of national industry and thus meet the growing and changing needs of the population. consists of lacquer satisfaction².

¹ Махмудов Н.М., Хомидов С.О. (2017) Ўзбекистон саноати: ривожланиш омиллари, тенденцияси ва муаммолари. 158-б ред. Тошкент: Иктисодиёт.

² Антонов З.Г., Л. В., 2013. Неоиндустриальная модернизация в современной России.. Томск, Известия Томского политехнического университета, pp. 34-39.

However, modernization of the industrial and food industries is a complex process that requires a lot of time and money. On the other hand, this complexity is explained by the relatively limited ability to quantify technological development and the lack of statistical data.

Therefore, it is advisable to use the opinion of experts in making decisions on the modernization of the food industry of the republic.

The advantage of this method is that if it is not possible to quantify complex development processes and require the formation of personal opinions about a particular process or object, this method is used and appropriate decisions are made based on the views of experts in the field³. The study focuses on the quantitative aspects of the expert survey method.

Analysis of the relevant literature

The analysis of scientific sources shows that the theoretical and practical aspects of the application of the expert survey method, in which the selected research topic belongs to a particular research topic, are described in detail in the research. Today, the expert survey method is a research method that is common to almost all disciplines. Therefore, this method is used in the formation of quantitative data on objects or socio-economic events, qualitative classification of indicators, development of various evaluation criteria, approval of developed national and international indices, analysis of socio-economic processes and weather. It is widely used in solving problems such as quantitative assessment of the state of affairs.

In general, the expert evaluation method in the scientific literature is an empirical method – a type of survey that involves people in the evaluation of an operation, event, or process being studied, and may have a general authoritative opinion. Sufficient basis for objective cleaning about the quality of the product under analysis⁴.

In qualimetry, the expert method is a set of special procedures, logical and mathematical methods used by experts to collect, summarize and analyze data⁵.

In any case, the list of factors influencing decision-making, their weight, as well as, it is necessary to involve a team of experts in the

rating to assess the quality of IT implementation or to improve its modules and data processing to get an overview. It is known that the essence of the expert assessment method is that experts conduct an intuitive-logical analysis of the problem with a quantitative assessment of feedback and formal processing of the results⁶.

However, the performance of expert systems is still far from ideal. The decline in their productivity may be due to the difficulty of translating jargon into the language of logic and mathematics, which is typical of the communication of specialists in a narrow specialty.

Moreover, principles based on expert knowledge are not always clearly articulated in terms of a given computer model. This is also complemented by the fact that knowledge based on personal experience may not be formalized to the extent that it can be generalized as a set of facts and general principles. The context does not play the final role here, its elements must be taken into account in decision-making, and what the expert sees on his own cannot always be modeled equally by the system⁷.

Therefore, the most effective situation is when a human expert works in conjunction with an expert system, while the latter works as an authorized partner and consultant on a particular topic.

Thus, the expert system does not try to replace the human specialist, but helps to expand the scope of knowledge of a reputable expert by combining the experience and knowledge of highly qualified specialists⁸.

In practice, there are many methods used to assess the level of competence of experts. In particular, if A.F. Garifulin used multidimensional index methods in assessing the level of competence of experts⁹, A.N. Anoxin used an arithmetic mean to assess the level of competence of each expert¹⁰. In his research, S.O. Khomidov also used arithmetic mean values in the selection of experts, their competence, the degree of consistency of expert opinion and the level of expert competence¹¹.

The next most important issue in expert

6 Evlanov L.G., Kutuzov V.A. Expert assessment in the management [Jekspertnye ocenki v upravlenii]. Moscow, Jekonomika, 1978 (In Russ.)

7 Джексон П. Введение в экспертные системы. – М.: Вильямс, 2001. – 624 с.

8 Муромцев Д.И. Введение в технологию экспертных систем. – СПб.: СПб ГУ ИТМО, 2005. – 93 с.

9 Гарифулин А.Ф. (2013) Экспертное оценивание при разработке эффективной стратегии. Справочник экономиста, 8(1), р. 4.

10 Анохин А.Н. (1996) Методы экспертных оценок. 82 ред. Москва: Обнинск: ИАТЭ

11 Хомидов С.О. (2019) Қайта ишловчи саноат тармоқларини модернизациялаш бўйича қарорлар қабул қилишда экспертлар фикридан фойдаланиш услуби. Иқтисод ва молия. №4 (124), 2019.

3 Орлов А.И. (2009) Организационно-экономическое моделирование: Учебник: в 3ч. 486 ред. Москва: МГУ им. Н.Э.Баумана

4 Профессиональная педагогика / под ред. С.Я. Батышева, А.М. Новикова. – М.: ЭГВЕС, 2009. – 456 с.

5 Бешелев С.Д., Гурвич Ф.Г. Математико-статистические методы экспертных оценок. – М.: Статистика, 1980. – 263 с

assessment is the assessment of the «degree of consistency of expert opinion.» This process is done by calculating the concordance coefficient. Based on the obtained values of this coefficient, appropriate decisions are made about a particular object or socio-economic processes.

The method of determining the concordance coefficient is almost the same in all the literature. However, the overlap of the estimates formed by the experts with respect to the object under evaluation or the socio-economic process complicates the method of calculating the concordance coefficient.

The process of calculating the concordance coefficient taking into account the considered aspects is described in the literature published by V.A. Mashin¹² and G.F. Romashkina and G.G. Tatarova, and the statistical significance of the concordance coefficient was estimated using Pearson's χ^2 criterion¹³.

Research methodology

Expert evaluation involves creating a type of mind that has greater capabilities than a person's capabilities. The source of multimind opportunities is the search for weak associations and assumptions based on the experience of the individual specialist. The expert approach allows you to solve problems that cannot be solved in the usual analytical way, including:

1. Choose the best of the available solutions;
2. Predicting the development of the process;
3. Finding possible solutions to complex problems.

The selection of experts based on the process of applying the expert assessment method, formation of expert groups, assessment of their level of competence, we perform steps to analyze the degree of coherence of expert opinions. The study also focuses on issues such as data processing by experts and making specific decisions based on the results obtained.

Generally, the number of experts in groups should be between 7 and 20. Sometimes this amount can be from 10 to 30. A very small number of experts leads to unreliable results, while a large number of experts causes organizational problems. Therefore, it is recommended to use the

following inequality in determining the required number of experts:

$$m \leq \frac{3}{2 \cdot Q_{\max}} \cdot \sum_{i=1}^m Q_i$$

In this case m^* - the total number of candidates, $Q_{\max}$ - the maximum value of the competency coefficient, Q_i - i -expert competence.

The following formula is sometimes used to determine the minimum number of experts¹⁴:

$$N = 0.5 \left(\frac{3}{\alpha} + 5 \right)$$

In this case, the parameter α is the minimum level of expert error, the value of which varies in the range $0 < \alpha \leq 1$.

There are expert assessments based on the level of completeness and this is expressed in terms of a matrix of the form and this is expressed in terms of a matrix of the form $A = \|a_{ij}\|_{m \times n}$ ¹⁵. In this case, m - the set of evaluated objects, n - the set of experts.

Then, for the first given matrix A , the matrix $C = A^T A$ is calculated. In this case, the A^T -matrix is the transposed matrix for the given initial matrix. Then, by performing various substitutions for the rows of the S -matrix, (3) matrices are formed.

$$S = \begin{vmatrix} c_{11} & c_{12} & \dots & c_{1n} \\ \tilde{n}_{21} & \tilde{n}_{22} & \dots & \tilde{n}_{2n} \\ \dots & \dots & \dots & \dots \\ c_{n1} & c_{n2} & \dots & c_{nn} \end{vmatrix} \Rightarrow y = \begin{vmatrix} \sqrt{c_{11} \cdot c_{12} \cdot \dots \cdot c_{1n}} \\ \sqrt{c_{21} \cdot c_{22} \cdot \dots \cdot c_{2n}} \\ \dots \\ \sqrt{c_{n1} \cdot c_{n2} \cdot \dots \cdot c_{nn}} \end{vmatrix} \Rightarrow x = \begin{vmatrix} y_1 \\ \sum_{i=1, n} y_i \\ y_2 \\ \sum_{i=1, n} y_i \\ \dots \\ y_n \\ \sum_{i=1, n} y_i \end{vmatrix}$$

The resulting matrix in expression (3) indicates the level of competence of the experts. As mentioned above, different methods are used to determine the level of competence of experts. One such method is determined using the following formula¹⁶:

$$K_j = \frac{\sum(X_{ij} \times M_i)}{\sum(M_i \times S_i)}$$

In this case, K_{i-j} - the coefficient of competence of the expert, X_{i-j} - assessment of the i - object by the expert, M_{i-i} - the average

12 Mashin V.A. (2008) Методическое руководство по оценке тестовых процедур, применяемых при работе с персоналом., Москва: www.mashinva.narod.ru.

13 Ромашкина Г.Ф., Татарова Г.Г. (2005) Социология.. Социология: методология, методы, математическое моделирование, 20(4АМ), pp. 139-140.

14 С.Д.Ильенкова, Л.М.Гохберг, С.Ю.Ягудин и др. (1997) Инновационный менеджмент: Учебник для вузов.. 327 ред. Москва: М.: Банки и биржи, ЮНИТИ.

15 Mashin V.A. (2008) Методическое руководство по оценке тестовых процедур, применяемых при работе с персоналом., Москва: www.mashinva.narod.ru.

16 Гарифулин А.Ф. (2013) Экспертное оценивание при разработке эффективной стратегии.. Справочник экономиста, 8(1), p. 4.

value of the object, S_i -i - the sum of the values of the object.

«Consensus of experts» is very important in the method of expert inquiry. If the level of agreement of the experts is high, then the results of the expert survey are considered reliable. To assess the degree of consistency of expert opinion, the «concordance coefficient» is calculated and is determined as follows¹⁷:

$$W = \frac{12 \times S}{d^2 \times (m^3 - m)}$$

In this case, the W - concordance coefficient, d - number of experts involved, m

Numerical values of the concordance coefficient	Levels of consistency of expert opinion
$0 \leq W \leq 0.2$	The compromise is very past
$0.2 \leq W \leq 0.37$	Compromise is the past
$0.37 \leq W \leq 0.64$	Consistency is average
$0.64 \leq W \leq 0.8$	Consistency is high
$0.8 \leq W \leq 1$	Consistency is very high

Table 1. Harrington's verbal-numbered scale

- the number of objects, S - a quantitative quantity in the concordance coefficient, it is defined as follows:

$$S = \sum_{i=1}^m \left(\sum_{s=1}^d r_{is} - \bar{r} \right)^2$$

In this case, r_{is} -i - the value or color given to the object by the s - expert, which is defined as follows:

$$r_i = \sum_{s=1}^d r_{is}, \quad (i = \overline{1, m})$$

The mean r_i of ($\bar{r}$) in equation (7) is found by the following formula:

$$\bar{r} = \frac{1}{m} \times \sum_{i=1}^m \sum_s r_{is}$$

If the evaluations of the objects evaluated by the experts overlap, then the concordance coefficient is determined as follows¹⁸:

$$W = \frac{12 \times S}{d^2 \times (m^3 - m) - d \times \sum_{s=1}^d T_s}$$

In this case, T_s -s - an interconnected color index between the ranked values, which can be found as follows:

$$T_s = \sum_{k=1}^{H_s} (h_k^3 - h_k)$$

The number of groups with equal colors between the H_s -s - ranked values, h_k -k - the number of equal colors in the group. If there are no comparison colors in the expert estimates, then $H_s=0, T_s=0$, and also $T_s=0$. It is recommended to use the Harrington verbal-numerical scale to assess the quality of the degree of coherence of expert opinion (Table 1).

According to the table, the degree of consistency of expert opinions varies from 0 to 1. The closer the values get together, the higher the degree of consistency of expert opinion, or vice versa. In practice, if $m > 7$, then the criterion x^2 - used to assess the significance of the concordance coefficient¹⁹. The distribution x^2 with the degree of freedom $v=m-1$ assumes the following value:

$$x^2 = \frac{12 \times S}{d \times m \times (m + 1) - \frac{1}{m - 1} \sum_{s=1}^d T_s}$$

If $W > x^2$, the degree of coherence of the expert opinion is reasonable, otherwise such coherence will be negligible. In practice, the «entropy concordance coefficient» is also used to assess the degree of consistency of expert opinion, and it is defined as follows²⁰:

$$W_e = 1 - \frac{H}{H_{max}}$$

If we take into account the evaluation of $p_{ij}=m_{ij}/m$ and $m_{ij}=m/n$, then the sum is equal:

$$H = -\frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n \sum_{j=1}^m \log_2 \frac{1}{n} = \sum_{j=1}^m \log_2 n = m \cdot \log_2 n$$

17 Губский М.И. (2011) Методика оценки состояния развития логистики в Республике Беларусь. Проблемы управления, 3(40), р. 123.

18 Жилиякова Е.В., Ларин С.Н. (2009) Методы и приемы проведения независимой экспертизы. Вестник ВГУ, 2(Экономика и управление), р. 113.

19 Галиновский А.Л., Самсонов К.С. и др. (2017) Сравнение различных методов контроля и диагностики качества керамики методом экспертного оценивания Инновация и экспертиза, 1(19), р. 68.

20 В.В.Давнис, (2005) Прогнозные модели экспертных предположений: монография. 45 ред. Воронеж: Воронеж. гос. ун-т.

In this case, p_{ij} – the estimate of the object and j -color probability, m -experts and the number of n -colors.

The entropy coordinate coefficient gives a slightly rougher result than the normal coefficient, and its value is 1 ($W_0=1$) when all objects are considered to be the same by experts.

The high value of the concordance coefficient obtained during the expert evaluation confirms the high degree of consistency of expert opinion. In this case, the opinions of experts on the object of assessment or socio-economic process are usually considered close.

There are many methods used in practice to measure the closeness of expert opinions.

One such method is determined using Ustyujanin's formula²¹:

$$S_{ij} = \frac{2 \cdot m_{ij}}{n_i \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{n_j}{n_i}\right) + n_j \log_2 \left(1 + \frac{n_i}{n_j}\right)}$$

In this case, S_{ij} – a criterion for the compatibility of the opinions of experts and j or «Informative measure of the closeness of the answers of two experts²²» m_{ij} – and j – the number of factors evaluated uniformly by experts, n_i and n_j – and j – the number of factors evaluated by experts, respectively. S_{ij} in the formula (15) is the sum ($\sum_{(j=1)}^n = S_{ij}$), i the

the opinion of the experts is completely inconsistent.

Analysis and discussion of results

Figure 1. Levels of competence of experts (in K_i -coefficient)²⁴

modernization in the food industry, 10 ($m = 10$) sectors of the food industry were selected and a total of 7 experts ($d = 7$) were used to assess these processes.

One of the members of the expert group asked, «How necessary is it now to replace the existing technology in the food industry?» was asked to answer the question of the content. In order to find an answer to this question, experts adopted a «10-point rating scale.» This rating scale rises from the bottom up, and its rising values reflect the need for experts to replace existing technology in the relevant food industries.

Objects (networks)	Experts						
	№1	№2	№3	№4	№5	№6	№7
Meat processing (O_1)	6	5	8	7	6	7	8
Milk processing (O_2)	7	8	5	6	7	6	5
Vegetable processing (O_3)	9	7	6	9	8	5	7
Fruit processing (O_4)	7	6	8	6	7	5	4
Vegetable oil production (O_5)	10	8	6	5	8	5	7
Manufacture of confectionery (O_6)	6	5	8	7	6	7	9
Beer production (O_7)	5	3	6	4	8	7	8
Production of canned food (O_8)	8	9	7	6	5	5	4
Production of carbonated water (O_9)	4	5	6	8	7	8	6
Manufacture of bread and bakery products (O_{10})	7	6	8	4	8	7	9

Table 2. Expert scores on the need to replace existing technology in key sectors of the food industry²³

index of expert competence, where it varies in the range $0 \leq S_{ij} \leq 1$. If, $S_{ij}=1$, then the opinions of these experts are completely consistent, and vice versa, that is, if $S_{ij}=0$, then it means that

Based on the data in Table 2, the competencies of the experts were assessed and formula (4) was used. The results of the analysis show that among the selected experts, the level of competence of expert 5

21 Мартеньянов Ю.Ф. (2010) Экспертные методы принятия решений. 16 ред. Тамбов: Изд-во Тамб. гос. техн. ун-та.

22 Пиганов М.Н., Подлипов Г.А. (2004) Экспертные оценки в управлении качеством радио-электронных средств. 55 ред. Самара: Самара. гос. аэрокосм. ун-та.

23 Source: The data was generated by the author using the expert survey method.

24 Author's calculations.

was the highest and the level of competence of expert 6 was the lowest (Figure 1).

Table 2 shows the scores of experts on the need to replace existing technology in key sectors of the food industry. The results of the

Figure 2. Trends in the coefficients of variation in the dynamics of scores given by experts to the main branches of the food industry (in percent)²⁵

expert assessment show that the scores given by the experts on the need for replacement of existing technology in the main sectors of the food industry were a minimum of 3.0 and a maximum of 10.0. According to the analysis, the average score in the vegetable processing industry was the highest at 7.2 ($\bar{r} = 7.2$), while in the beer industry it was $\bar{r} = 5.8$ represents the lowest value.

The coefficients of variation in the dynamics of scores shown by experts to the main branches of the food industry have the following trend (Figure 2).

As can be seen from the graph, the object of O7, ie the «degree of stratification²⁶» (coefficient of variation $V = 30.85$) in the dynamics of the scores expressed by experts in the decision to modernize the beer industry, was stronger than the stratification in the

dynamics of the scores shown in the decision to modernize other sectors. In the meat processing industry (O1), this stratification ($V = 15.34$) was relatively low.

Conclusions and suggestions

The results of the analysis show that the level of consensus of experts in making decisions on modernization of the network, that is, with a concordance coefficient of $W = 0.025$, this value is in the 2nd order range of the Harrington verbal scale.

Based on the obtained value of the concordance coefficient, it was concluded that, the level of consensus of experts in the decision to replace existing technology in the food industry is low. In this case, we compare by the criterion χ^2 ($\chi^2 = 1.56$) and the degree of consistency of the opinion of the experts turns out to be insignificant. It serves as a basis for the scientific conclusion that there is no need to introduce new technologies in the food industry.

According to the results of the expert assessment, the stratification of the dynamics of the points indicated by the experts in the decision to modernize the beer industry ($V = 30.85$), turned out to be stronger than the stratification in the dynamics of the scores shown by the experts in the decision to modernize other sectors. The results of the analysis show that the degree of consensus of experts in the decision to replace the existing technology in the food industry is insignificant ($W = 0.025$), it was found that it was not expedient to introduce new technology in the food industry at present.

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